

反击中共福奇 CDC 政权信息战、造谣的方法

The method of countering the disinformation attack of the CCP Fauci CDC regime

索要数据的明细，明细到每个医院、县、社区，方便审计核对。审计的方法除了大数据逻辑分析，另一个方法就是把大的数据拆细到具体责任单位、人，然后统计抽样核对。

Ask for the details of the data of each hospital, county, and community to facilitate auditing and verification. In addition to the logical analysis of big data, the audit method is to break down the big data into specific responsible units and persons, and then statistically sample and check.

大数据分析：打疫苗的新冠感染数量+不打疫苗的新冠感染数量 $\cong$ 有疫苗以来总的新冠感染人数=累计感染数量-有疫苗以前的感染数量. 不打疫苗的新冠感染数量+其他病毒感染数+打了疫苗的新冠感染数=总病人数。这里存在分类错误风险：其他疾病感染数可能因故意或疏忽错分类为打疫苗或不打疫苗的新冠病毒感染数。

Big data analysis: the number of new covid cases of the vaccinated + the number of new covid cases not vaccinated $\cong$ The total number of COVID-19 infections since the vaccine is available = the cumulative number of infections-the number of infections before the vaccine is available. The number of COVID-19 infections that are not vaccinated + the number of other virus infections + the number of COVID-19 infections that

have been vaccinated = the total number of patients. There is a risk of misclassification: the number of infections of other diseases may be deliberately or negligently classified as the number of new coronavirus infections that are vaccinated or not vaccinated.

由于离岸避税岛存在，CDC、NIH 官员可能与药商、中共政权利益勾连，使得其他疾病感染数因故意错分类为不打疫苗的新冠病毒感染数的可能性增大。为了审计是否发生了这种错误分类，也需要细节测试，即审计构成该数据的明细。

Due to the existence of offshore tax havens, CDC and NIH officials may be linked to the interests of drug dealers and the Chinese Communist regime, making it more likely that the number of infections of other diseases will be deliberately misclassified as the number of new coronavirus infections that are not vaccinated. In order to audit whether such misclassification has occurred, detailed testing is also required, that is, the details of the data that constitute the audit.

另一个风险是打了疫苗但染疫的人数被隐瞒、少报，这个也会导致数据之间打架。

Another risk is that the number of people who have been vaccinated but infected will be concealed and underreported. This will also lead to fights between data.

另一个错误分类的可能性是中共福奇 CDC 政权错误将有疫苗以前的感染病例数据算到有疫苗后的感染数据，这种错误分类会导致有疫苗后合计数超过有疫苗后的感染总数。

Another possibility of misclassification is that the Fauci CDC regime mistakenly counted the data of infection cases before the vaccine was available to the infection data after the vaccine was available. This misclassification will cause the summed number of infections after the vaccine was available to exceed the total number of infections after the vaccine was available.